

Synthesis of 1-Acetyl/Pentafluorophenyl-3-fluorinatedaryl-5-phenyl/furfuryl-4H-4,5-pyrazolines as Antifertility Agents

KRISHNA C. JOSHI*, V. N. PATHAK and SHARDA SHARMA

Department of Chemistry, University of Rajasthan, Jaipur-302 004

Various substituted fluoro-chalcones were prepared from appropriate ketones and aldehydes and two new chalcones are reported. On condensation with hydrazine hydrate or pentafluorophenylhydrazine in acetic acid, the chalcones gave the title compounds, 1-acetyl/pentafluorophenyl-3-fluorinatedaryl-5-phenyl/furfuryl-4H-4,5-pyrazolines (IIa-i). The compounds were screened for antiimplantation activity in adult female rats at 10 mg/kg.

THE pyrazole nucleus is reported to possess contraceptive and abortifacient activities¹⁻³. Pyrazoline derivatives were synthesised and screened as antifertility agent by Sangwan and Rastogi⁴ but none of these compounds could prevent pregnancy at a dose of 10 mg/kg. Keeping in view the observations that the introduction of fluorine leads to altered biological activity in many systems, we thought it worthwhile to incorporate fluorine into pyrazoline system and study whether this would lead to better antiimplantation activity in the title compounds.

The substituted fluorinated chalcones were prepared by the base catalysed condensation of fluorinated ketones and aldehydes. Two of the chalcones, 1-(3,4-difluorophenyl)-3-phenyl-2-propen-1-one and 1-(3,4-difluorophenyl)-3-(2'-furyl)-2-propen-1-one derived from 3,4-difluoroacetophenone, are being reported for the first time. On condensation with hydrazine hydrate or pentafluorophenylhydrazine in acetic acid, the chalcones gave the title compounds (IIa-i).

Representative compounds were screened for their antiimplantation activity in adult female rats.

Experimental

The compounds were characterised by melting points, elemental analysis, ir, ¹H nmr and mass spectral studies. Melting points were taken on a Toshniwal apparatus and are uncorrected. Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin Elmer-157 G spectrophotometer. ¹H nmr spectra (CDCl₃) were recorded on a Bruker HX-90 spectrometer using TMS as internal standard. Mass spectra were recorded on Kratos-30 and 50 spectrometers. Purity of the compounds was checked on silica gel G tlc plates using benzene or benzene-ethyl acetate (1 : 1).

Fluorinated chalcones: Various chalcones derived from fluorinated ketones and aldehydes (Ia-i) were prepared by the literature method⁵⁻⁸.

1-(3,4-Difluorophenyl)-3-phenyl-2-propen-1-one: 3,4-Difluoroacetophenone (0.01 mol) was treated with benzaldehyde (0.01 mol) in minimum amount of ethanol and stirred at room temperature for 30 min. Sufficient NaOH solution (2 N) was added to it, to render the stirred solution alkaline and the whole reaction mixture was further stirred for about 30 min. This was then neutralised with HCl (1 N) and diluted with water. The precipitated chalcone was filtered and recrystallised from ethanol to yield the product (60%), m.p. 85° (Found: C, 73.6; H, 4.2. C₁₅H₁₀F₂O requires C, 73.7; H, 4.1%); $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 1650 cm⁻¹ (C=O highly conjugated); ¹H nmr (CDCl₃): δ 7.2 (d, C _{α} -H), 7.9 (d, C _{β} -H) and 6.5-8.0 (complex multiplet, aromatic protons).

1-(3,4-Difluorophenyl)-3-(2'-furyl)-2-propen-1-one: This was prepared by similar procedure from 3,4-difluoroacetophenone (0.01 mol) and furfuraldehyde (0.01 mol). Yield 60.6%, m.p. 155° (Found: C, 66.5; H, 3.5. C₁₅H₈F₂O₂ requires C, 66.6; H, 3.4%). $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 1650 cm⁻¹ (C=O highly conjugated); ¹H nmr (CDCl₃): δ 7.25 (d, C _{α} -H), 7.9 (d, C _{β} -H) and 6.5-8.0 (complex multiplet, aromatic protons).

1-Acetyl-3-(4'-fluorophenyl)-5-phenyl-4H-4,5-pyrazoline: A mixture of 4-fluoro-chalcone (0.01 mol), hydrazine hydrate (0.012 mol) and glacial acetic acid

JOSHI, PATHAK & SHARMA : SYNTHESIS OF 1-ACETYL/PENTAFLUOROPHENYL-3-FLUORINATED- ETC.

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL DATA OF SUBSTITUTED PYRAZOLINES

Compd. no.	X	Y	Z	M p. °C	Yield %	Molecular formula	N% Found/(Calcd)
IIa	4-F	C ₆ H ₅	COCH ₃	140	86.6	C ₁₇ H ₁₁ FN ₃ O	10.1 (9.9)
IIb	2,3,4,5,6-PentaF	C ₆ H ₅	COCH ₃		80.0	C ₁₇ H ₁₁ F ₅ N ₃ O	8.1 (7.9)
IIc	2,4-diF	C ₆ H ₅	COCH ₃	160	75.0	C ₁₇ H ₁₁ F ₂ N ₃ O	9.5 (9.8)
IId	4-F,3-Me	C ₆ H ₅	COCH ₃	150	80.0	C ₁₈ H ₁₃ FN ₃ O	9.8 (9.5)
IIe	4-F	α-furyl	COCH ₃	85	86.0	C ₁₉ H ₁₃ FN ₃ O ₂	11.8 (11.4)
IIf	3,4-diF	α-furyl	COCH ₃	155	80.0	C ₁₉ H ₁₃ F ₂ N ₃ O	10.3 (10.5)
IIg	3-Cl, 4-F	C ₆ H ₅	COCH ₃	120	85.0	C ₁₇ H ₁₁ ClFN ₃ O	8.7 (8.8)
IIh	5-F, 2-Me	C ₆ H ₅	COCH ₃	110	85.0	C ₁₈ H ₁₃ FN ₃ O	9.6 (9.8)
III	4-F	C ₆ H ₅	C ₂ F ₅	150	75.0	C ₂₁ H ₁₁ F ₆ N ₃	6.8 (6.4)

(10 ml) was refluxed for 6-8 h. The mixture was cooled and poured into crushed ice. The resultant solid mass was filtered, washed with water and recrystallised from methanol to yield the product (86.6%), m.p. 140° (Found: N, 10. C₁₇H₁₁FN₃O requires N, 9.9%); $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 2800-2900 (CH₂), 1635-1665 (C=O, C=N), 1100-1400 cm⁻¹ (=C-F); ¹H nmr (CDCl₃): δ 2.3 (s, COCH₃), 3.2-3.7 (dd, CH₂), 5.6 (s, -C-H) and 6.5-8.0 (complex multiplet, aromatic protons); M⁺ at m/z 282.

The other compounds IIb-i (Table 1) were prepared similarly using appropriate chalcone and hydrazine. In the mass spectra, the parent peak M⁺ at m/z 354 (IIb), 300 (IIc) and 296 (IId) correspond to their molecular weights.

Antifertility activity. Four representative compounds (IIa-d) were screened for their antimplantation activity. Testing was done on adult female rats of the Charles Foster strain weighing between 120-200 g body weight. The compounds were suspended in distilled water with the help of gum acacia and administered orally at 10 mg/kg P.C. once daily for 7 days. The rats were examined on day P.C. The results are summarised in Table 2.

TABLE 2—POST-COITAL ANTIFERTILITY EFFICACY IN ADULT FEMALE RATS

Compound no.	Dose* mg/kg	Total rats	Pregnant ^b rats	Implantations ^b mean ± SE, range
IIa	10	5	5	6.40 ± 1.11 (4-10)
IIb	10	5	4	8.25 ± 1.41 (4-10)
IIc	10	5	5	6.66 ± 1.21 (2-9)
IId	10	6	5	6.80 ± 0.86 (4-9)

* Days 1-5 Post-coitum, oral. ^b Day 10 Post-coitum.

Acknowledgement

The authors are grateful to Dr. S. K. Roy and Dr. M. M. Singh, Department of Endocrinology, Central Drug Research Institute, Lucknow for evaluation of antifertility activity and Dr. A. Shah, Institut für Organische Chemie und Biochemie, der Universität Bonn, West Germany for providing the spectra. We are also thankful to Indian Council of Medical Research, New Delhi for financial assistance.

References

1. B. V. COOMBS and W. J. HOULIHAN, *Chem. Abstr.*, 1976, 85, 78124
2. D. A. HARBCK and W. J. HOULIHAN, *Chem. Abstr.*, 1976, 85, 163083.
3. E. V. BOUSQUET, M. D. MORAN, J. HARMON, A. L. JOHNSON and J. U. SUMMERS, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1975, 40, 2208.
4. N. K. SANGWAN and S. N. RASTOGI, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1979, 18, 65.
5. U. G. JOSHI and G. O. AMIN, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1961, 38, 159.
6. N. M. SHAH and S. R. PARIKH, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1962, 36, 776.
7. K. O. JOSHI and A. K. JAUHAR, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1962, 39, 465.
8. K. O. JOSHI and A. K. JAUHAR, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1965, 42, 787.
9. R. FILLER, U. O. BEAUCAIRE and H. H. KANG, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1975, 40, 935.